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Title: SOP for shutting down and turning on the GC Q – Exactive

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Summary

This section describes how to use shut down the system for a maintenance or service procedure.

- **IMPORTANT:**
- When turning Off the GC: first turn off the temperature and then turn off the carrier gas flow
- When turning ON the GC: first turn on the carrier gas flow
- For cooling Front Inlet, Oven and X-line 1 and X-line 2 don't use > Maintenance > Cool for maintenance. After turning On software will automatically load values from last used instrument method. Before turning off the instrument load instrument method for cooling (cool_down_before_shutdown_PK.meth) or set the temperature of Front Inlet, Oven and X-line1 and X-line 2 to 20°C manually and then put to off mode
- Before turning off move the injector to position 1

To turn off the GC Q – Exactive

1. Turn off autosampler (see Figure 4)
2. Move the TriPlus RSH autosampler Head to the position 1 (see Figure 2 position 1)

NOTE: After turning off LS Tool (Injector) could fall down, position 1 prevents to destroy LS Tool (Injector)

Figure 1 TriPlus RSH autosampler

3. Load instrument method for cooling the instrument. Go to D:\data\GC methods in use> sent cool_down_before_shutdown_PK.meth. Wait until temperatures are (120 - 80°C) ~ 60-90 min

- 2) Turn the carrier gas flow of front inlet Off (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (SSL) > Column flow > Off)

- 3) Click the **Off** button to take the mass spectrometer to Off mode
- 4) Turn off the carrier gas Helium (small valve)
5. Push down the power switch (breaker) for Electronic Boards, located at the back of the instrument, to the position **O** (down) and unplug the power cable from AC Input (see Figure 2)

Figure 2. Main power of Electronic Board

- 2) Power off the GC:
 - a. Push down the power switch (breaker), located at the back of the instrument (transfer line) and unplug the power cable from AC Input (see Figure 3)

Figure 3 Main power of GC transfer-line

- b. Unplug the power cable from AC Input located at the back of the instrument
(see Figure 4)

Figure 4 Main power of the autosampler

- 3) Turn off the Nitrogen (cylinder)
- 4) Turn off the Thermo Q - Exactive GC software to Off mode
- 5) Push down the power switch (breaker) to take the Electronics to **Servis mode**
- 6) Push down the power switch (breaker) to take the Q - Exactive to **Off mode**
- 7) Turn off the computer and unplug the power cable
- 8) Turn off the pump and remove the power cable

To turn on the GC Q – Exactive

- 1) Plug the power cable from pump on and turn on the pump
- 2) Plug the power cable and turn **On** the computer
- 3) Turn on the carrier gas Helium
- 4) Turn on the Nitrogen
- 5) Plug the power cables (1 and 3) from AC Input (see Figure 5)

Figure 5 Main power AC input of Q - Exactive

- 6) Push the Main power switch (beaker) to the position On (see Figure 6)

Electronics service switch
Main Power switch

Figure 6 Main power switch Q - Exactive

NOTE: The pumps switch on automatically and the device waits for connection. Wait 10 minutes for switching pumps to on mode.

- 7) Push up the power switch (breaker) to take the electronics of Q - Exactive to on mode
- 8) Push up the Electronic Boards to **On** mode (see Figure 2)

NOTE: Electronic Boards (inside the Electronic module) generates voltages to supply the electronics boards, injector and detectors modules, motors, fans, and oven heater.

- 9) Power on the GC:
 - a. Plug the power cable to AC Input and push up the power switch (breaker), located at the back of the instrument (transfer-line) (see Figure 3)
 - b. Plug the power cable to AC Input located at the back of the instrument (autosampler) (see Figure 4)
- 10) Turn the carrier gas flow (0.8 ml/min) of front inlet On (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (SSL) > Column flow > On) and wait 10 minutes. Go to Thermo Q - Exactive GC software > EI/CI source > MS transfer line temp. (°C) 150, Ion source temp. (°C) 150 and oven to 70-80 (°C) and set the temperature of X-line 1 and X-line 2 to 150 (°C) at the same time

NOTE: Check if the gas flow gradually increases and then is constant > in system is no leak

11) Increase the carrier gas flow to 1.2 ml/min and wait 10 minutes

12) Set temperature of Front Inlet (SSL) to 280 (°C) and wait 30 minutes

NOTE: Wait until the Instrument Status > Vacuum system is Ok – HV enabled; Ultra High Vacuum at least 1e-08 mbar. GC Q Exactive should go automatically to **Standby mode** (in Thermo Q Exactive GC software)

13) Bakeout the system > go to Thermo Q Exactive GC software > Off mode >

Vacuum/Bakeout > set Bakeout time (h) 12 > set Enter standby after Bakeout > Start

NOTE: After Bake out Ultra High Vacuum should reach at least 1e-10 mbar (ideally up to 1e-11 mbar)